

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

Nonprofit Business Model Canvas

This guide explains the use of the Nonprofit Business Model Canvas as a strategic management tool and provides a planning template.

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The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management tool and a planning template, developed by Alexander Osterwalder and widely used by organizations designing their business models and operations. It is a hands-on tool with nine "building blocks" (Key Partners, Key Activities and Key Resources, Value Propositions, Customer Relationships, Customer Segments, Channels, Cost Structure, and Revenue Streams) to be used in strategic planning sessions as a part of group work to visualize the connections between different elements to form a cohesive business model.

The Nonprofit version of the Business Model Canvas includes Operations and Engagement planning categories and modifies some building blocks – expanding to a 'Social Value Proposition'; replacing 'Customer Relationships' with 'Relations', 'Customer Segments' with 'Stakeholders' and 'Revenue Streams' with 'Value capture'. It's displayed below with two more fields added from the Impact Business Model Canvas – Mission statement and Intended impact.

An interactive planning template is available at <https://www.figma.com/community/file/1459157929377881180>

A printable planning template is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14621236>

Adapted from the Nonprofit Business Model Canvas (<https://tinyurl.com/4wexxnuv>), based on the Business Model Canvas (<https://tinyurl.com/53vhtcze>) by Business Model Generation and Strategyzer and inspired by the Impact Business Model Canvas (IBMC) (<https://www.impactbusinessmodelcanvas.com/>)

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How you can use the Canvas

You can use the Canvas to map your context and needs, current resources, including funding and partnerships, and brainstorm on the new options available and a sustainability plan via cooperative work schemes.

For example, Research Consulting used the No-profit Business Model Canvas in their projects with Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs (COPIM), Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) and Open Research Europe and described their experiences in [Unlocking Business Potential: How the Business Model Canvas can help organisations thrive](#).

For COPIM, Research Consulting used the Canvas during the business model sprint for [Thoth Open Metadata](#) to develop a shared understanding of potential business models, identify possible revenue streams and the risks associated with these, and outline next steps for the organisation.

For DOAJ, Research Consulting used the Canvas to reflect on the various users of DOAJ data and the extent to which they contribute to financially supporting the platform to inform discussions about the organisation's core activities and value add and the need to update the current fee structures (see more details in [this blog post](#)). After this exercise, DOAJ updated its [library and institutional supporter model](#) and [publisher supporter model](#).

For the Open Research Europe publishing platform, Research Consulting developed seven case studies of similar open scholarly infrastructures and used the Canvas to map their strategies in a [range of options](#) for the European Commission to consider.

Things to consider

"The simplicity of the Business Model Canvas is, however, a double-edged sword: by breaking down complex business concepts, it can support focussed discussions, but this may also lead to oversimplification. Additionally, the canvas captures a snapshot of an organisation's business model at a particular point in time, without accounting for the dynamic nature of markets, customer preferences and external factors. The Business Model Canvas is not a panacea, but we have found it to be a valuable tool for bringing clarity to organisational design and strategy development projects." ([Research Consulting \(2023\). Unlocking Business Potential: How the Business Model Canvas can help organisations thrive](#))

References

[Joanna Ball, Andrea Chiarelli \(2023\). Striking a balance between openness and free access in scholarly infrastructure – DOAJ at 20. LSE](#)

[Impact Business Model Canvas](#)

[Research Consulting. Operationalising Open Research Europe as a collective publishing enterprise](#)

[Research Consulting \(2023\). Unlocking Business Potential: How the Business Model Canvas can help organisations thrive](#)

[Strategyzer. The Business Model Canvas](#)

[Wikipedia. Business Model Canvas](#)

Feedback

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DISCLAIMER

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